

NEOLOGISMS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *this article is devoted to the study of English Language Neologisms. Day by day life is changing and attitude towards the language is also becoming more important.*

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It is a well-known fact that the word-stock of any language is constantly changing and renewing. Old words die and new words appear. Before disappearing, a word undergoes the stages of being obsolescent, obsolete and archaic. The beginning of the aging process of a word is marked by decrease in its usage. Rarely used words are called obsolescent. To English obsolescent words belong the pronoun though and its forms thee, thy and thine, the verbs with the ending - est {though makest) and the ending -th {he maketh), and other historical survivals. Obsolete words have gone completely out of usage though they are still recognized by the native speakers (methinks = it seems to me; nay = no). Archaic words belong to Old English and are not ^cognized nowadays. The main function of old words is to create a realistic background to historical works of literature.

Neologisms are newly born words. Most of them are terms. The layer of terminological neologisms has been rapidly growing since the start of the technological revolution. The sphere of the Internet alone gave birth to thousands of new terms which have become international (network, server, browser, e-mail, provider, site, Internet Message Access Protocol, Hypertext Transfer Protocol, Microsoft Outlook Express, Internet Explorer, Netscape Communicator, etc).

The Internet is an immense virtual world with its own language and its people, good or bad. Hacker means "someone who uses a computer to connect to other people's computers secretly and often illegally in order to find or change information". Spammer means "someone who sends emails to large numbers of people on the Internet, especially when these are not wanted". Recent discoveries in biochemistry, genetic engineering, plasma physics, microelectronics, oceanography, cosmonautics and other sciences demanded new words to name new concepts and ideas. The vocabulary of our everyday usage is also being enlarged by neologisms. Bancomatj, means "a European system of automatic cashejecting machines". Bank card means "a

small plastic card that you use for making payments or for getting, money from the bank". The social and cultural reference of neologisms proves that they are more the products of our conceptual system and not simply meaningful language signs. They codify new cultural experience of society and provide evidence concerning the current trends of its development. For this reason by studying neologisms of a certain language we can learn about present-day cultural values, way of thinking and living of the community which speaks this language. [1. 146] For example, neologism couch commerce 'buying goods online from one's home' may indicate popularisation and wide-spread occurrence of the Internet industry; staycation (from to stay and vacation) meaning 'a holiday spent in one's home country rather than abroad' may indicate current economic crisis which affects people's lives. The fact that neologisms are often chosen as the 'words of the year' (WotY) also adds to the advantages of teaching these lexical units to students. WotY is a set of assessments as to the word or expression which reflects the most important concept in the public sphere during a specific year. In the USA among the chosen words of the year were bushlips (1990), 'insincere promise of a politician, reference to «Read my lips: no new taxes» by then U.S. President George H.W. Bush', prefix e- [1, 146] 'as in e-mail or e-commerce', hashtag (2012) etc. (available at www.americandialect.org). Thus, by teaching neologisms one can demonstrate the vitality of the language.

Sociologists around the world claim there is a change in the perception of time in the 21st century. People seem to feel rushed, busy, there is a time-scarcity problem [2. 113]. Naturally, this change has been registered by language. In the English language there appeared such neologisms as hurry sickness 'an urgent and persistent need to feel busy or productive', timesuck 'activity which makes one waste his/her time', sightjogging 'visiting a foreign city by jogging around it'. The principle of language economy or the principle of least effort also helps speakers to save time to achieve maximum communication result. In conclusion we want to add that in every sphere of our life neologisms are getting spread day by day. Each person who studies foreign language must take into consideration that neologisms are also one part of the learning language, and it should be taught in a proper way, in order to understand each other and be appropriate during one's speech.

Types of Neologisms

As there are a variety of ways to make new words, there are a variety of types of neologisms. Here are a few specific types of neologisms:

Portmanteaus or Blend Words

A specific type of neologism, portmanteaus do just what they say: blend together two words to create a new word which combines their meanings.

Here are a few examples of blend words:

smoke + fog = smog

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spoon + fork = spork

breakfast + lunch = brunch

Derived words

Derived words are words that use ancient Greek and Latin phrases naturalized to match the English language.

Here are a few examples of derived words:

Latin word: villa

Meaning: villa or house

Derived words: villa, village, villager

Latin word: sub

Meaning: under

Derived words: submarine, subway

Latin word: copia

Meaning: plenty

Derived words: cornucopia, copious

Transferred words

Transferred words take derived words to a whole new level, as they encompass words taken from another language and used in an adjusted form in English.

herbs from French herbes meaning herbs

alligator from Spanish el lagarto meaning lizard

wiener dog from German wiener meaning hot dog

New words come from creativity and invention, merging of existing words, and borrowing from other cultures and languages.

The Importance of Neologism

Neologisms remind us that language is not something set in stone, but an evolving body of work, subject to adjustment, deletions, additions, and change. As new things are invented, as slang becomes acceptable, and as new technologies emerge, new words must fill in the gaps in language. Just in 2014, a variety of new words were added to the dictionary including hashtag, selfie, and pho.

References:

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